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UDK: 342.7-053.2(=214.58)(497.11)

UDK: 316.356(=214.58)(497.11)

UDK: 351.941(497.11)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17811925

ROMSKA DECA I IZAZOVI SAVREMENE ZAŠTITE PRAVA DETETA: ULOGA LOKALNOG OMBUDSMANA U OBLIKOVANJU POLITIKA I PRAKSI

Povodom 35. godišnjice primene Konvencije Ujedinjenih nacija o pravima deteta, ovaj rad osvrće se na savremene izazove u ostvarivanju i zaštiti prava dece na nacionalnom i međunarodnom nivou, sa posebnim naglaskom na ulogu lokalnog ombudsmana u tim procesima. Iako je normativni okvir Republike Srbije u značajnoj meri usklađen sa međunarodnim standardima, praksa ukazuje da deca i dalje ostaju posebno ranjiva grupa, izložena različitim oblicima rizika – od nasilja, digitalnih pretnji i zloupotrebe novih tehnologija, do siromaštva, diskriminacije i ograničene dostupnosti usluga podrške, naročito u lokalnim sredinama. Poseban prostor posvećen je položaju romske dece, koja se neretko suočavaju sa višestrukom diskriminacijom, slabijom dostupnošću obrazovanja, neadekvatnim uslovima stanovanja i većim rizikom od zanemarivanja i eksploatacije. Kroz rad lokalnog ombudsmana u Nišu, posebna pažnja usmerena je na unapređenje zaštite ove grupe dece kroz terenske posete romskim naseljima, posredovanje između institucija i porodica, iniciranje hitnih intervencija u slučajevima uskraćivanja osnovnih prava, kao i organizovanje edukativnih aktivnosti usmerenih ka roditeljima i stručnim službama. Uloga lokalnog ombudsmana posebno dolazi do izražaja kroz njegovu dostupnost građanima, neposredan uvid u probleme na terenu i mogućnost brzog reagovanja u situacijama koje zahtevaju zaštitu prava deteta. Iskustvo iz Niša pokazuje da ovakav pristup jača poverenje građana i povećava vidljivost institucije kao realnog mehanizma zaštite. Zaključak rada ukazuje na potrebu daljeg jačanja institucionalnih kapaciteta, razvoja preventivnih politika i stvaranja društvenog okruženja u kojem se prava sve dece a posebno romske dece i druge visokorizične grupe - dosledno štite, poštuju i afirmišu u skladu sa duhom Konvencije.

Ključne reči: prava deteta, lokalni ombudsman, romska deca, diskriminacija, savremeni izazovi, zaštitni mehanizmi, javne politike, Konvencija UN o pravima deteta.

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ROMA CHILDREN AND CHALLENGES OF CHILDREN'S RIGHTS PROTECTION: THE ROLE OF THE LOCAL OMBUDSMAN IS SHAPING POLICIES AND PRACTICES

On the occasion of the 35th anniversary of the implementation of the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, this paper examines contemporary challenges in the exercise and protection of children's rights at both the national and international levels, with specific reference to the role of the local Ombudsman in these processes. Although the normative framework of the Republic of Serbia is largely aligned with international standards, practice shows that children remain a particularly vulnerable group, exposed to various risks, ranging from violence, digital threats and misuse of new technologies to poverty, discrimination and limited access to support services, especially in local communities. Special attention is given to the position of Roma children who often face multiple discrimination, reduced access to education, inadequate living conditions, and an increased risk of neglect and exploitation. With reference to the activities of the local Ombudsman in Niš, the paper focuses on improving the protection of this group of children through field visits to Roma settlements, mediation between institutions and families, initiating urgent interventions in cases of denial of basic rights, and organizing educational activities aimed at parents and professional services. In particular, the role of the local Ombudsman is significant in terms of his/her accessibility to citizens, direct insight into problems on the ground, and the ability to respond quickly in situations requiring the protection of children's rights. The experience of the local Ombudsman in the City of Niš demonstrates that such an approach strengthens public trust and increases the visibility of the institution as an effective protection mechanism. In the conclusion, the author underscores the need to further strengthen institutional capacities, to develop prevention policies, and to create a social environment where the rights of all children, and especially the rights of Roma children and other high-risk groups, would be consistently respected, protected and promoted in accordance with the spirit of the Child Convention.

Keywords: children's rights, local ombudsman, Roma children, discrimination, contemporary challenges, protection mechanisms, public policies, UN Convention on the Rights of the Child.